

From paper to byte. An interim report on the digital transformation of two thing editions

Frederic Auth^{a,b}, Katja Rösler^a, Wenke Domscheit^a, Kerstin P. Hofmann^a

^aRömisch-Germanische-Kommission des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts

^bGoethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main

September 2023

Abstract

One specific form of publication for archaeological objects are catalogues, atlases and corpora. Kerstin Hofmann has introduced the term ‘*Ding-Editionen*’ (thing editions) for this category of publications that present their data in lists, short catalogue texts, and on plates. As publications of archaeological sources, they are central reference works, and serve as examples for the recording of new finds and features. Therefore, thing editions are powerful instruments that up till to today are shaping the representational style and the language for archaeological objects, be it their names or their formal description. In a project of the Central Scientific Services (CSS) of the German Archaeological Institute (DAI) we are digitising thing editions as they comprise normed data on archaeological objects. This data is being made easily accessible to researchers, research projects, students and other interested parties via the digital research environment of the DAI – the [iDAI.World](#). In our paper we report on the challenges, conceptualisations and implementation of two digitisation projects on roman-era material culture, the *Corpus der römischen Funde im europäischen Barbaricum* and the *Conspectus Formarum Terrae Sigillatae Modo Confectae*. In analysing knowledge production through digital transformation, we focus on normalisations and show that Bruno Latour’s concept of circulating reference and inscription can be usefully applied to the analysis of digitisation of thing editions.

Introduction

Analogue ordering systems on paper are used as a heuristic means of investigating larger amounts of things and play a role in data collection, storage, evaluation and publication of objects. This is especially true for *Ding-Editionen* (thing editions), a term coined with reference to text editions for catalogues, atlases and corpora of material objects (Hofmann 2018; Hofmann et al. 2019). As publications of archaeological sources, thing editions are central reference works, and serve as examples for the recording of new finds and their features. They present objects and their relations in form of lists and tables, seriations and typologies, catalogue texts and on plates. Thing editions provide a specific thesaurus employed by its entries, comparable to *Normdaten* (authority data; i.e., [GND data](#)).

Due to the increasing publication of archaeological data in general and object data collections in particular on the WWW, it is becoming more and more important to transfer existing *Normdaten* from paper into the digital environment. Hereby, the data must not simply be made available in a different medium. It is equally necessary to provide the opportunity to also (re-)contextualise the data collection with information on the historical conditions of the editing projects, archaeological concepts implied as well as the use and circulation of data structure and description. This is particularly important if the data is to be made available as linked open usable data (LOUD; cf. Thiery 2019).

The following pages present concepts of digital transformation of two edition projects on Roman finds conducted by the *Römisch-Germanische-Kommission* (Romano-Germanic Commission [RGK] of the German Archaeological Institute [DAI]) and its partners. Since its foundation in 1902, the RGK has been committed to international cross-border research in Europe and supports wide-ranging, international networking and scientific exchange across the boundaries of specialist traditions and languages. This is also reflected in its publication projects; from its beginnings, the RGK has been committed to overarching research representations and thing editions (Rösler et al. 2022). Since 2019 NOA – Normdata for Objects in Archaeology, a subproject to a DAI research data-project by Central Scientific Services (CSS) on the development of user-oriented digital modules for data on forms and shapes of archaeological objects, we are working on digital transformation of thing editions to be added to the existing tools and services of the [iDAI.World](#). Elaborating on the transformation of the *Corpus der römischen Funde im europäischen Barbaricum* (Corpus of Roman Finds in the Barbaricum; CRFB) and the *Conspectus Formarum Terrae Sigillatae Modo Confectae* (*Conspectus*) into linked open usable data, we ask how two different concepts of order for archaeological objects, chrono-type and form, function as part of circulating references (Latour 2002). This paper is a preliminary report on the theoretical and conceptual settings as well as beta versions of applications and does not include user case studies; these will be carried out and the results will be published in the further course of the project. The following is subdivided into four chapters – first some remarks on types in catalogues as inscriptions, followed by an analysis of the digital transformation of the CRFB, and the *Conspectus*. In a final synthesis, the concepts of type and form employed in the thing editions and the consequences for digitisation are compared.

Archaeological types in catalogues as inscriptions

The term type in Archaeology is used for the conceptualisation and the synopsis of real or ideal (i.e., drawings of non-existing objects displaying all defined features of a certain type) objects that are perceived as nearly identical or very similar because they have common properties and are considered characteristic, for example, of a time, a region, a style, etc. The use of the word type does not necessarily indicate the employment of a typology; rather, types are often also spoken of in the course of classifications and categorisations, for example in the case of series, classes, categories or (sub-)groups. In research they are often used as index types for cross dating as well as indicators for chronological periods (chrono-types), geographic spaces (choro-types) and even tribes, cultures or groups (eidico-types) (Hofmann 2014, 132).

In the context of knowledge production (not only in archaeology, but also in linguistic, history, botany, zoology, art etc., cf. Bohn 1988; Bowker/Star 2000; Müller-Wille and Charmantier 2012; Müller-Wille 2017), the constitution of types is based on the observable regular recurrence, that is the repeatedly observed presence of approximate sameness, which is interpreted as an indication of what is common and/or characteristic, i.e., typical. Types then are defined on the basis of selective characteristics and their manifestations, which enable classifications through the abstracted combinations of properties. Frequently, they are also given a name, employing everything from indices (A45; see below) to property words (crossbow-brooch with wide foot = *Almgren Gruppe I*; Almgren 1923, 7) to short descriptions (“Platter or plate with sloping wall and plain rim”; Ettliger et al. 1990, 52). Types in the broader sense can thus also subsume forms and form groups.

Definitions and denominations *per se* create normalisations/standardisations as they are written and published in text form and thus manifest text as a representative for the physical thing. To describe those manifestations, French philosopher Bruno Latour (2002, 306–307) uses the term inscriptions, derived from the latin verb *inscribere* = to write on, to address, to brand, to name and to record something (s. v. *inscribio* in Oxford Latin Dictionary 1968, 921), to denote transformations of things into scientific entities. These can be indices, labels or data entries in tables and textual representations like lists, diagrams or

charts. Inscriptions are considered as fixed results in research processes. In the further course of research, they are usually no longer questioned and thus remain unchangeable for the time being. They are used as facts, they are worked with, they are entities that are context-independent, can be linked and reproduced.

In this article, we will focus on this normalisation by inscriptions of types published in thing editions and in online data representations. We are not concerned with the making or publishing process but with the possibilities and limitations of working with listed information in the context of catalogues, understood as specific textual forms of condensed recordings, arranged following a system (cf. Eco 2009). In order to describe these possibilities and limitations, we are guided by the concept of circulating reference and in particular by the notion of trade-offs described by Latour (cf. Latour 2002) that occur in the process of knowledge production (fig. 1). In his study on practices involved in the collection of soil examples in the Amazon Forest, Latour identifies circulating references in the process of information production, as it is marked by the analysis of phenomena with the help of recursive access to existing knowledge and techniques (maps, publications, technical devices). Latour’s process model is a reversible chain of transformation steps where phenomena (in our case: archaeological objects conceptualised as types) circulate, at each step losing some properties and gaining others (Latour 2002, 71). Loss and win are assessed in a trade-off the researcher carries out, in that they either reduce or amplify the phenomenon’s locality, particularity, materiality, variety and continuity on the one hand, and compatibility, relative universality, text, standardisation and calculation on the other (Latour 2002, 24–79, see esp. 70–72 fig. 2.21–2.23).

Thus, inscriptions and trade-offs are elements of research processes that employ circulating referencing. By using Latour’s concepts, we would like to emphasise that, instead of viewing knowledge as a state, product or result, knowledge is seen here as a complex and dynamic process that is set in motion and kept in motion by various actors, media, practices and settings (Hofmann and Schreiber 2015, 17–19). It is necessary for knowledge to be circulated, connected and regularly updated.

Figure 1: Latour’s circulating reference model (above), depicting the process of knowledge production. Below Latour’s representation of trade-offs, what is gained (amplification) and what is lost (reduction) in the course of transformation of things in the world into epistemic objects (after Latour 2002, 70–71 fig. 2.21–2.22).

The Corpus of Roman Finds in European Barbaricum (CRFB)

Project history and catalogue structure

The CRFB is a longstanding research and edition project of the RGK and dates back to 1979/80, when a group of researchers from the former GDR, Poland and former Czechoslovakia agreed on the research goal of compiling a catalogue of Roman finds outside the Roman Empire under the roof of the Central Institute for History and Archaeology of the GDR (*Zentralinstitut für Alte Geschichte und Archäologie ZIAGA*) (cf. Benecke and v. Rummel 2021; Voss and Hüssen 2017; Auth and Voss 2021; Grumeza 2020; Schreiber 2018). After the German reunification, the RGK continued the project and pursued the editing and publication of the corpora. Starting in 1994, fourteen volumes and a number of supplements have been published within the CRFB-project up till today. Currently there are eight volumes and one supplement covering the Roman finds according to modern Federal States of Germany (as find registration is their respective responsibility; CRFB D 1–8.1), as well as three volumes and four supplements covering the Polish regions of Lesser Poland, Masuria, and Central Poland (CRFB PL 1–3; CRFB PL Supplement 1–4) and one volume each for regions in Romania (CRFB RO1), Hungary (CRFB U1) and Lithuania (CRFB Litauen). The eight printed volumes for the German contribution to the CRFB-project currently consist of around 8,100 catalogue entries through every kind of archaeological finds group. Approximately 2,100 of those consist of coins.

Corpus-Rubriken	
1	Fundplatz, Lage; kurze Beschreibung der Fundstelle
2	Fundart, Komplexnummer
3	Funddatum /Fundzeit
4	Literatur zum gesamten Fundplatz bzw. Fundkomplex
5	Gegenstand, Schlüsselnummer
6a	Beschreibung der spezifischen Merkmale (Fundbeschreibung)
6b	technologische Erkenntnisse
6c	naturwissenschaftliche Untersuchungen und Analyseergebnisse
7	germanische Beifunde
8a	Datierung des römischen Gegenstandes
8b	Datierung der germanischen Beifunde
9a	Literatur zum Gegenstand
9b	Besitznachweis (Verbleib)
9c	Analogie, besondere Anmerkungen
10	Bearbeiter

Figure 2: The CRFB's 15 rubrics are: **1** findspot, location, short description of the findspot; **2** feature context; **3** date of discovery; **4** literature on the findspot; **5** general object designation, unique ID; **6a** description of the specific characteristics (finds description); **6b** technological findings; **6c** archaeometrical investigation and analysis results; **7** associated regional finds; **8a** dating of the Roman object; **8b** dating of the associated regional finds; **9a** literature on the object; **9b** whereabouts at time of recording; **9c** analogy, special notes; **10** editor.

The CRFB is a spiritual successor to the research and publication project *Atlas der Urgeschichte* and its first volume *Der römische Import im freien Germanien* published by Hans-Jürgen Eggers in 1951.¹ Roughly 1,300 entries, already – although with less detail – published by Eggers, have been included into the eight volumes of CRFB covering modern Germany. The data concept of the CRFB is based on the research work by historian Rudolf Laser at ZIAGA in the 1980s. He developed a schema for compiling

¹On biographic details for Hans-Jürgen Eggers see https://sempub.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/propylaeum_vitae/

an analogue catalogue of 942 Roman finds and findspots in Altmark (Saxony-Anhalt) and what today is Thuringia. The catalogue, still based on the principle of indexing on cards, is recorded on notch-hole index cards and made accessible for a set of queries via a thesaurus on sight-hole index cards.

However, it already did include all 15 *Rubriken* (rubrics: read as categories; fig. 2) relevant to the CRFB on finds, find complexes and sites. This schema then was used in a computer-based database developed in the late 1980s,² but which was later unfortunately abandoned. Nevertheless, until today the database model sets the framework for the CRFB's presentation of finds and therefore its usage.

1 Fdpl. 1: „Langmathen“ oder „Krusenberg“, Höhe 56,16, s des „Fuchsbruches“, ca. 2 km n des Ortes; Gelände des frühkztl. Brandgräberfeldes.
2 Brandgrab 6
3 1886/87
5 **Fibel** *Taf. 12,4* **IV-02-8/1.1**
6a bronz. Aucissafibel (Almgr. 242, Riha Typ 5.2.4, 704), leicht gewölbter Bügel mit feiner Perdreihe zw. 2 flachen Längsfurchen. Fuß u. Ndh. vom Bügel abgesetzt, Fußknopf, Scharnier mit Achsendknöpfen, Nadel fehlt; L. 53 mm.
7 rädchenverzierte Urne, eis. Messer, 5 Knochen-nadeln.
8a frühe KZT
8b B 1
9a Eggers, Import 112 Nr. 832; R. Stimming, Frührö-mische Funde aus der Mark Brandenburg und ihrer Umgebung. Mannus 7, 1915, 345 Taf. 38,6; Felsberg, Elbhavelland 129; Guthjahr, Semnonen 56; v. Müller, Provinzialrömische Fibeln 113 Abb. 1; Seyer, Besiedlungsgeschichte 51; 156 Taf. 11a.
9b Märk. Mus. Berlin, Slg. Stimming II6 (Ber- lin-Charlottenburg)
10 H. Geisler

Figure 3: Catalogue entry of the CRFB on a fibula covering most rubrics (CRFB D1, 28).

Of these 15 rubrics only the rubrics, findspot (fig. 2.1), general object designation (fig. 2.5; e.g., bronze vessel, glass bead, coin), the finds description (fig. 2.6a) and editor, that is the author of the catalogue entry (fig. 2.10), is mandatory for every entry (though it is possible that some of them are only used as an implicit reference). The object categorisation is done according to a list of functional groups, spanning across the whole of the spectrum of Roman finds. Catalogue entries are sorted according to an index (e.g., CRFB D 1, IV-02-8/1.1), consisting partly of a municipality key and an alphabetical list of findspots within the municipality. The index and the general object designation together build the leading information in every entry (fig. 3, printed bold). As a result, the catalogue is capturing a wide variability of objects into a narrow and predefined template.

The type concept employed in the CRFB

The CRFB-project aims to record the finds in a catalogue together with their type designations and the corresponding type-dependent dating, both for Roman finds (see rubric 8a) as well as associated regional finds (see rubric 8b) (fig. 3). Though archaeological types in research are often used as index types for cross dating (cf. Hofmann 2014), the CRFB does not express this kind of information. Instead, it provides a *Datierungsrahmen* (dating frame/ dating range) in rubrics 8a and 8b, stating: "*Eine feste, absolutchronologische Fixierung ist damit nicht beabsichtigt*" (a solid, absolute chronological fixation is not intended (cf. CRFB D2, 7)). Intended or not, certainly the representation of type dating in rubrics 8a and 8b of the catalogue does exactly what it is designed to do: it dates the objects listed in the catalogue entry. Four dating scenarios are present in the catalogue (tab. 1): The dating of Roman finds is given

²From this, the volumes D1 (Brandenburg and Berlin), D3 (Mecklenburg-Vorpommern) and D5 (Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg and Schleswig-Holstein) have been derived from (Auth and Voss 2021).

(8a) while the rubric for regional finds (8b) is question-marked (scenario A) and vice versa (B),³ dating information is given in both rubrics (C), or both rubrics are question-marked (CRFB D 3, III-08-2/1.1).

Scenarios	Dating information for Roman find (8a)	Dating information for regional find (8b)
A	Yes	No
B	No	Yes
C	Yes	Yes
D	No	No

Table 1: Possible combinations for dating rubrics 8a (Roman find) and 8b (regional finds).

25% of all catalogue entries contain actual type designations for Roman finds together with their corresponding chronological information (corresponds to scenario A and C). The remaining entries for scenarios A and C are only presenting incomplete or vague typological and chronological information. One eighth of catalogue entries are displaying chronological information for regional finds (B), ranging from accurate dating to vague estimations spanning multiple centuries. 60% of the entries – although they may possess some form of information on types – do not display any easily accessible dating information (D). In the following, we will present two catalogue entries to demonstrate the use of type inscriptions in the catalogue. The first belongs to scenario C and presents data on a bronze casserole from the burial ground of Großromstedt in Thuringia (CRFB D 8.1, 131 XVII-17-8/1.18; iDAI.gazetteer-ID [2116131](#)). The second example belongs to scenario B and contains, amongst others, a glass bead from the burial ground of Perdöhl in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (CRFB D 3, 71–73II-04-15/1.9; iDAI.gazetteer-ID [2049913](#)). The bronze casserole in the data set of entry XVII-17-8/1.18 has been assigned the type *Eggers 131*, therefore the dating for the catalogue entry is given as *mittelaugusteisch bis tiber.* (middle augustan to tiberian period) that, in terms of annual figures, relates to the time of 15 BC until 37 AD. The dating for the associated find of a fibula type *Almgren 45* in rubric 8b is given as *RKZ B 1a*, an inscription which refers to the chronological stage (*Stufeneinteilung*) by Jerzy Wielowiejski published in 1970 (Wielowiejski 1970, 74–76; 83, Tab. XV) that further narrows down the period of time to approx. 10 to 40 AD (fig. 4).

Therefore, even if not explicitly mentioned, a specific kind of cross dating is implied as type *Eggers 131* (8a) is giving a *terminus post quem*, whereas type *Almgren 45* (8b) is giving a *terminus non ante quem*. The types now are not solely providing one *Datierungsrahmen* but two, and the difference between them evokes a need for explanation. Hence, research oftentimes draws on narratives in the sense of stories that assert correlations between entities – in our case the different chronological date spans that could lead to the deduction that the Roman object might possibly be older than the germanic (or, of course, vice versa) – by establishing relationships and making what has happened understandable (Jung 2017, 163–164).

But these narratives only can serve as explanations if the data they refer to is reliable. The reader will encounter three challenges when working with the CRFB:

1) Visual inspection and scientific assessment have *per se* only been carried out on Roman finds and not on the associated regional finds (cf. CRFB D2, 10). This restriction of scientific assessment to one category of finds is practically necessary due to the large number of objects, but the catalogue’s representation of the data in the form of inscriptions suggests a reliability that might not exist in reality.

2) Museums and collections etc. have been impacted by substantial war losses, which made it necessary to collect inscribed data for the CRFB merely through lists of finds in archives, museums or from publications (cf. CRFB D1, 16; CRFB D6, 13–14), a practice not only of the CRFB’s data collection, but a general archaeological practice of collecting data (Schreiber 2018, 134–146).

³Rubric 8b is missing in the catalogue entry if the entry only consists of a Roman find (e.g., III-07-16/1.1).

Abb.2. Vergleichende Übersicht zur Chronologie im Römischen Reich und in Germanien mit den wichtigsten Ereignissen und Herrschern.

Figure 4: Comparative overview of chronologies for the Roman Empire and Germania (CRFB D1, 10).

3) Find recordings and a coherent representation across modern borders, national as well as federal or regional, create challenges that result from research traditions as well as bureaucratic restrictions. This leads to differing naming conventions, terminologies, and procedures for recording finds.

The second common scenario covers catalogue entries with glass beads, recorded in the CRFB by findspot or by some kind of context (i.e., a group of graves). Hence, entries can consist of lists of up to a four-figure-number of beads. The type designations are made by the respective authors according to the state of research at the time of the catalogue's compilation and with more or less accuracy (e.g., CRFB entry: II-04-15/1.9). Within one list type designations can range from descriptive information like *Glasperle: mehrfarbig, zerschmolzen* (glass bead: multicoloured, melted) to inscribed assignments like *TM 379b Var.* (CRFB D3, 72), the latter being a specific inscription created by Magdalena Tempelmann-Mączyńska (1985) within the context of her doctoral thesis on glass beads of the Roman Iron Age and Migration Period. The inscription *TM 379b Var.* gives the following information: Tempelmann-Mączyńska's typology contains beads inscribed with *379b* (TM 1985, pl. 13). The number is designating the type, the small Latin letter denoting a variant of the type,⁴ and thus signifies a hierarchical position in her classification system. The term variant refers to individual objects that can be assigned to a superordinate entity, but which differ from it in minimal ways (described in detail in Tempelmann-Mączyńska 1985, 15–18). The abbreviation *Var.* at the end of the CRFB inscription is most likely another typological distinction made by the editor of the catalogue entry (fig. 2.10), in this example Hartmuth Stange (CRFB D3, 73), which, however, is not verifiable on the basis of the catalogue. Although listing an array of objects with clear determined types, again only a *Datierungsrahmen* (cf. p. 13) is given of which the user does not know whether it is derived by the editor of the entry on the basis of one single type designation or whether it is a summarisation of the different dating of the types. Both, the derivation of the inscription *Var.* in *TM 379b Var.* and the inscription *C2-D* remain unclear.

The trade-off on the CRFB's chrono-types

The trade-off inherent to inscriptions can be well demonstrated by the examples just mentioned. In regard to the inscriptions *Eggers 131* and *Almgren 45*, they are well established and consistently used type designations since their publication in 1951 and 1923 respectively, which is the result of the general stability of form and the widespread distribution of these objects.

Almgren 45 or *A45* are common inscriptions for a so-called eye fibula and the descriptions of its form, distribution and chronological position by Oscar Almgren (Almgren 1923, 23; 25, pl. III 45) are basically still applicable (cf. Kunow 1998). On the other hand, the localities of the original object depicted on Plate III 45 (the plate numbering together with the author's surname forms the type designation), that is its findspot Sojvide, Parish Sjonhem in Gotland (iDAI.gazetteer-ID [2780449](#)) or its repository in the collection of the Museum Stockholm with the inventory number 5398 a (iDAI.objects-ID [1168559](#)), have fallen into oblivion. In terms of Latour's trade-off, the inscription of the eye fibula from Gotland as *Almgren 45* and its use in the CRFB is made with the following reduction and amplification: The object's findspot, find context and repository (localities and continuity) as well as the specific features, i.e., certain stylistic or functional elements, of the object and its properties like the exact material composition of the bronze or traces of usage (materiality and particularity) are being reduced.

⁴*379b* = flower-shaped beads (cf. Tempelmann-Mączyńska 1985, 62), TM being the initials of her surname.

On the other hand, the inscription's universal applicability is amplified because the object's descriptions (text written by Almgren) can be applied to finds of fibulae (standardisation) – as the one found in Großromstedt – together with its information on date and distribution, which are even transferrable to the whole find complex; thus, they support the validation of inscription *C2–D*. The same principle can be observed in catalogue entry XVII-17-8/1.18, concerning the bronze casserole of type *Eggers 131*.

The inscription *TM 379b* made by Tempelmann-Maczyńska in the process of the development of the typology of glass beads implies reduced information on their find spots (localities), their uniqueness (particularities), the differing chemical compositions of the material (materialities), and the individual finds contexts (continuities) of each bead that is subsumed under this inscription. Then again, other kinds of information of beads named *TM 379b* are amplified. They are compatible with other type designations as now being part of a typological system, they are standardised and thus named and described (text) and the possibility of calculations is amplified as measurements can be cross-charged. Moreover, the circulation of the beads *TM 379b* in research is amplified as well as their universality in that the inscription makes the subsumed beads immutable and generalisable. In the CRFB, the information the inscription has been given by Tempelmann-Maczyńska in her trade-off are now being used to order a find in a list by its type designation and for the confirmation of the *Datierungsrahmen C2–D*. Thus, in the CRFB, the specific bead, casserole and fibula found in graves in specific localities are not merely grave gifts for a deceased anymore but instead function as chronological indicators in a thing edition.

Dating with a tree: A typonchronological module for the CRFB types

As described above, dating and type assignment of Roman finds are closely intertwined in the CRFB, but – because of the challenges mentioned above – the catalogue entries quality varies. Hence, the information on the object's assigned type as well as the dating can be unreliable, as the extreme example of the type variant *TM 379b* has shown, in that it was again tacitly assigned as a variant of a variant to *TM 379b Var.* for the glass bead in the CRFB catalogue entry.

The unreliability of the data is largely due to lack of information. While it is not possible to trace all research steps that have been carried out to conduct the catalogue entries of the CRFB on our own, we decided to transfer the data of catalogue entries into an online accessible database and contextualise the inscriptions of the data in order to provide the users with information according to the current state of research. This enables the users to better assess the data on their own.

At publication of this contribution, the CRFB volumes are in the process of being converted into an online database, embedded into the digital research infrastructure of the German Archaeological Institute, [iDAI.world](https://www.dainst.org/). The database is conceptualised as a means to make large quantities of data usable through searches, visualisation and geo-referencing. But, the example of catalogue entry II-04-15/1.9 (glass beads; fig. 5) shows another necessity while transforming the CRFB into an online database: Lists of objects need to be transformed into single-object-records to address them individually. In result the original ca. 8,100 of catalogue entries will be transformed into more than 50,000 single-object-records. This singularity in turn will make the data-sets universally available as linked open data, which for example is a requirement to connect the coins-records from the CRFB volumes to the project-database *Antike Fundmünzen in Europa* (afe.dainst.org), which will be used to give numismatic information on the coins.

In order to tackle the unreliability of assignments and inscriptions, we decided to employ a tree as our model as its structure is a very common and long used epistemological tool for combining entities. It is not our goal to provide an explanation or a closer dating frame/ dating range for single catalogue entries, like the example mentioned above. We aim to provide a solution to make analysis possible in the first place by streamlining dating information on single objects.

Figure 6: Excerpt on bronze casseroles from the tree structure for the typochronological module.

Tree models were already used in the 13th century (termed *arbor scientiarum*) as auxiliary to corpora of encyclopaedias and are closely connected to learning and memorising by pointing out connections of knowledge unified or rooted in one subject (Rossi 2000, 36–44). The tree containing the CRFB’s collected typological and chronological information, is conceived as the digital ‘typochronological module’. It is a stand-alone application conceptualised as a way to mitigate the aforementioned challenges when handling large collections of objects. The main target of the module is to accumulate type-denominations and their connected dating as of the latest research and build a concordance of types. It is thus a kind of thesaurus of types and their dating, and was developed by experts on specific finds groups.

The compiled concordances are presented as tree branches (fig. 6), the nodes nearest to the root have been set as general terms, subsuming large functional groups, like ‘Jewellery, attire and parts thereof’ subsuming amongst others all glass beads, or ‘vessels’, subsuming vessels of all kinds and material groups. Type definitions in nodes further down the tree’s branches are becoming continuously more specific up until the point of the most specific agreed upon definition by research. This is usually a type-variation which is not further subdivided in literature (leaf-node). They are usually type definitions based on the similarity of multiple characteristics and their *Datierungsrahmen* and spatial distribution is specific. The lower branches are usually set and probably won’t be challenged in the future, i.e., a type of casserole won’t be classified as a type of plate. The branches at the top of the tree shall always represent the latest state of research according to the project’s finds specialists. Future research may define more variants of a type and in consequence add more branches and nodes to the tree or change grouping.

The implementation of the typochronological module leads to several observations. Considering the examples laid down earlier, we would like to elaborate on the following three:

- 1) Between the tree-root and the last node (i.e., *Eggers 131*) lie nodes of increasing typological accuracy (fig. 6). A strand ending at type *Eggers 131* will start at the root ‘vessel’ and go through the nodes ‘bronze vessels’ – ‘casseroles’ – ‘Group *Eggers 131–153*’ – ‘Subgroup *Eggers 131–135 Schwanenkopfkasserollen*’ – ‘*Eggers 131*’. Every node is annotated with further information which usually consists of at least dating information. While the upper nodes can only provide vague dating (for the node ‘casserole’ dating would be given as ‘1st c. BCE – 3rd c. CE’), the dating is getting more accurate further down the tree (at the leaf ‘*Eggers 131*’: 1st c. CE). But even though dating information of the ‘middle nodes’ is usually approximate; it nevertheless is useful within the digital representation of the CRFB. As already mentioned, only 25% of catalogue entries fall into the scenarios A and C and possess concrete type information. This means, three quarters of the data within the CRFB contain object information but no type designation and therefore no dating information for the Roman finds.

2) Using the tree, it will be possible to use this baseline object descriptions to provide at least a *Datierungsrahmen* for objects without type designation. This also applies for rough type designations where only a range of possible types is given (II-04-21/1.4; ‘cauldron, *Eggers 4–6*’). As a result, all of the more than 50 000 entries will have some kind of designation, with their according dating information.

3) In consequence, the user will then be able to assess the inscription *TM 379b Var.* as being solely an estimation to the variant of Tempelmann-Maczyńskas type *TM 379*.

In the course of development, a MariaDB database⁵ was chosen to store the data for the typochronological module. The tree structure is recreated by the relations between single entries. The relations are limited to an ‘is-Child’/‘is-parent’ relationship. All other relational connections are derived from the resulting scheme. Concordances and alternate designations can be added as desired. Due to the ‘flat storage’⁶ in the database, the front-end accessing the data will be flexible. An application programming interface (API) is used to access data within the database, making it possible to access single datasets (‘one node/leaf’), or whole strands of the complete tree, or the complete tree itself. When searching the CRFB online or the stand-alone typochronological module, it is insignificant which naming convention is preferred. All concordances and different ‘names’ will be searched and listed equally. The aim for the publicly available module is to include the most used naming conventions and typological systems.

The *Conspectus Formarum Terrae Sigillatae Modo Confectae*

Project history and catalogue structure

The *Conspectus* is a widely accepted and continuously used reference work for plain, i.e., undecorated Italian-type *terra sigillata* produced and distributed throughout the Roman world in the first century BC and the first century AD. The catalogue was compiled in the years between 1986 and 1990 by leading specialists for Roman pottery, all of them members of the learned society *Rei Cretariae Romanae Fautores* (<https://fautores.org/>; <https://blog.fautores.org/>), an institutionalised, worldwide network on Roman pottery studies. The specialist’s aim was to overcome classifications that are usually limited to certain regions and are based on the analysis of production sites, contexts or chronology (Ettlinger et al 1990, 2). Since its publication by the RGK in 1990, the *Conspectus* has served as a standard for the designation and representation of *terra sigillata*.

The *Conspectus* is divided into two parts. The first part presents information on production sites and manufacturing techniques, on geo-chemical compositions of clays as well as on dated sites, graves and find ensembles. The second part provides the catalogue of 54 classes, referred to as forms, of plain *terra sigillata* on fact sheets, combining textual information and profile drawings side-by-side (fig. 7). A comprehensive overview (fig. 8) offers a quick entry to the forms.

Furthermore, vessel parts are treated in excursuses (Ettlinger et al. 1990, 153–163). As pottery is often found fragmented, inscriptions are provided for forms of bases (*Consp. B n.n.*), rim forms of relief-decorated vessels (*Consp. R n.n.*) and forms of flagons (*Consp. K n.n.*; cf. Ettlinger et al. 1990, 45, 152–189). All in all, the *Conspectus* serves as a manual not only to the researcher but to everyone interested in plain Italian type *terra sigillata*. The authors especially emphasise the simple applicability of their system as it should be usable "not only by pottery specialists [...] but also by other archaeologists and historians who are not specialists, but who may need to deal with *sigillata* evidence bearing upon problems of their own" (Ettlinger et. al 1990, 1).

⁵MariaDB is a relational database system, derived from MySQL™ and together with MySQL™ is one of the most widely used databases in the world.

⁶Data-sets are stored side-by-side within a table, hierarchy is only achieved through specific markers in the data-sets themselves.

Consp. n.n.: The type concept of the *Conspetus*

By defining the quotation of the forms being *Consp. n.n.* (Ettlinger et al. 1990, 45), a simple but clear addressing of objects is established. The *Conspetus'* forms of *terra sigillata* were compiled with the intentions of „sufficient“ completeness and being "understandable without reference" in a „comprehensive scheme“ (Ettlinger et. al. 1990, 1). In order to achieve these objectives, the particularities of type definitions and denominations of *terra sigillata* found at archaeological sites have to be generalised. Inscriptions and groupings of *terra sigillata* need to be independent of functional, chronological or regional contextualization and authorship. The reference to a group being for example *Consp. 1.1.* (fig. 7): In the catalogue text a description of the form, other findspots and concordances to other type designations are referring specifically to *Consp. 1.1.*, whereas information on production, date and distribution also apply to *Consp. 1.2.* Next to the description, profile drawings of several examples are displayed together with a numbering on the basis of the inscription *Consp. 1.1.* and *Consp. 1.2.*, i.e., the number 1.1.1, 1.2.1 etc. designating the profile drawing of the object depicted. By representing the forms with several different examples, the authors emphasise on the variability inherent to type designations. Under the heading 'references', the findspot, the publication of the illustration and the potter's stamp of the actual object are quoted in the catalogue. To sum it up, *Form 1* is the denomination of a group that contains forms, each termed with a second number, i.e., *Consp. 1.1.* These are groupings of actual vessels that are depicted on the table each labelled with a third number: *Consp. 1.1.1.* The development of this principle of denomination can be illustrated by a graph archived in the meeting protocols of the authors owned by the RGK (fig. 9).

Figure 7: Fact sheet of *Consp. 1* with textual information and profile drawings (Ettlinger et al. 1990, 52–53).

Figure 8: Overview of the *Conspectus* object forms from *Consp.* 1, platter or plate with sloping wall and plain rim, to *Consp.* 54, lids with knobs (Ettliger et al. 1990, suppl. 2).

The illustration by author Philip M. Kenrick (here shortened to K), placed in the protocol of a discussion on the appropriate system as well as notation and punctuation of the inscriptions *Consp n.n.* on the same level in the *Form* (here called No. 9 and 10) (Archiv RGK CFZab-4, 16).

The core of the *Conspectus*' type concept, then, is the following: Not one object as a representative or an ideal representation cumulated from many similar objects, but a variety of objects of similar shape but with distinctive object-related particularities such as size or usage in our example platter for serving food and plates for eating, is inscribed as a form. With regard to the inscription *Consp. 1.1.*, it is most important, that it is related by the authors to preceding specific inscriptions (Ettliger et al. 1990, 52): *Goudineau 1*, a type designation by Christian Goudineau (Goudineau 1968) for *terra sigillata* found in Bolsena, Italy (iDAI.gazetteer-ID 218075), and *Pucci 3, 1-7* as well as *Mazzeo 4*, both type designations inscribed by Giuseppe Pucci and Lucia Mazzeo Saracino in the *Atlante delle forme ceramiche II* (Atlante 1985).

The *Conspectus*' system of grouping can be described as a taxonomy, that is a system without rank, such as identification taxonomies, which rather serve to box a given thing in order to find it again quickly. A taxonomy could, for example, simply be an order that follows the alphabet. In this light, the term taxonomy denotes practices of delimitation that aim to create a picture (a tableau in Foucault's sense) of visible differences without striving for explanation, whereas the eventual hierarchisation of the taxa is secondary to these practices and belongs to the processes of explanation and abstraction (Rösler 2019, 125–133). A taxonomy is merely a system of drawers into which things can be sorted, filed, and retrieved with the very important property of being provisional, expandable and easily modifiable.

And because of this conception of grouping in the *Conspectus*, several trade-offs are also inherent. In terms of Latour the following trade-off concerning the inscription *Consp 1.1* is accepted: Reduction of

K: proposals for numerotation:

not the system of Morel!

W: doesn't like the dash

Figure 9: Graph by P. M. Kenrick illustrates different principles of denomination for *Consp. 9* and *Consp. 10* discussed by the authors during the development of the *Conspectus* (Archiv RGK CFZab-4, 16).

information on find spots (localities), individual finds contexts (continuities) and neglect of uniqueness of the object, i.e., differing chemical compositions of the material used for each object (materialities), colour, size (particularities). It is solely the object's shape of the *terra sigillata* that is taken into consideration. This leads to the amplification of type denominations and form description (standardisation). But in relation to this trade-off, inscription *Form 1* amplifies standardisation even more as even more objects fit – objects whose particularities are then further reduced. On the other hand, the numbering 1.1.1 inscribes an actual object and with the help of qualitative references, its particularities, findspot and potter's stamp, are amplified.

As the authors emphasise, this standardisation serves the systematisation of future knowledge production: "We have tried to systematise that knowledge in such a way that future researchers will find it helpful as a framework within which to arrange their own perceptions and on which to hang future accretions of knowledge" (Ettlinger et al 1990, 2). They thus anticipate precisely those processes of recursive access to existing knowledge that Latour describes as circulating references.

(Re-)Connecting data: *Consp. n.n.* in the *iDAI.world*

The concept of types in the *Conspectus* is solely based on shape and is characterised by a high degree of standardisation in form description. Extensive concordances and type definitions are summarising preceding research. The underlying concept as well as the concordances support archaeological type assignment even beyond existing classifications. We have made this advantage usable within the systems of the *iDAI.world*. The data management system for information on objects and images, including catalogues and its plates, is iDAI.objects/Arachne. (cf. arachne.dainst.org/info/about on its technical components and in-depth literature, hereinafter addressed as *iDAI.objects*). *iDAI.objects* has been developed from the necessity to collect and serve archaeological and *altertumswissenschaftliche* (ancient studies) data, which otherwise would end up in project specific, short lifespan, small, single-purpose databases. *iDAI.objects* currently contains more than 4.5 million entries. Its original design as an image database for management, archiving and viewing pictures as well as a full text search, enabling the query for every piece of

information, facilitates the incorporation of object concepts like form or type that do rely both on textual definition and pictorial representation.

With the help of the import tool *AIX* (<https://arachne.uni-koeln.de/aiax/>) we implemented the fact sheets of all 54 *Conspectus* forms. As far as possible, the structure of the paper catalogue text is recreated on the user interface and, with the help of the iDAI.objects catalogue tool, accessible to all users, the fact sheets are reassembled into a compilation comparable to the paper catalogue. Thus, the viewing and usage habits of previous users of the written work are taken into account. In iDAI.objects the catalogue data can be connected with information and images that already exist. For example, an old data entry made in 2009 in the context of the digitalisation of dia-positives⁷ on the *terra sigillata* plates from the publication on the early Roman empire military camp Haltern am See (iDAI.gazetteer-ID 2051849) with the type inscription *Ha1* (<https://arachne.dainst.org/entity/21179>) can now be linked to *Consp. 12.3–5* (Ettlinger et al. 1990, 72; 190).

Furthermore, since iDAI.objects is surrounded by the systems of the iDAI.world, geographical (iDAI.gazetteer), chronological (iDAI.chronontology) and bibliographical (iDAI.zenon) data is integrated into the digital data of the *Conspectus*. The other way round, specific data of the *terra sigillata* listed in the catalogue is incorporated into the data stock of the iDAI.world. In contrast to the paper inscription, maps of the find sites and distribution maps of the forms are now produced on the fly; with one mouse-click, the location of the publications listed in the bibliography can be called up in the DAI libraries; and chronological designations can be translated via iDAI.chronontology into absolute years and vice versa.

Digital perspectives: A slider-puzzle and a diagram of relations

To make past research results more visible, two concepts for the digital representation of knowledge have been developed, which could function as ways of accessing the *Conspectus* data in iDAI.objects. The first concept, inspired by slider puzzles, addresses the retrieval of different parts of drawings to enable the comparison of traits. Another concept involves a dynamic display of different relations between the datasets – be it chronological, spatial, functional, stylistic or concordances to other type designations – that allows the individual sorting and arrangement of objects and data by the user.

1) The 'Archaeological FormSlider': In the context of excavations or rapid documentation often fragments of vessels must be typologically assessed. As the *Conspectus* is conceptualised as a hands-on manual, it already provides type designations and descriptions of bases, which have no direct relation to the rim design of a vessel, as well as special rim forms are treated individually by the authors in excursions with their own citation form (see above; Ettlinger et al. 1990, 153–189). But still, in practice the researcher is comparing the profile of the sherd in their hands with the profile drawings of the *Conspectus* forms by tinkering a template or browsing and searching the pages. In the digital environment it is possible to facilitate this activity and even enhance the representation of both data and profile drawings.

Inspired by [antlitz.ninja](#), an app that allows the combination of different parts of portraits and that is based on the well-known slider puzzles for children, we wanted to transfer the effects of these games into the handling of the *Conspectus* drawings. Slider puzzles encourage the precise observation of features by enabling individual compositions of image parts. Thereby, the player might perceive characteristics he did not perceive while studying the whole picture. Furthermore, these games make the not - or not yet - existing a subject of consideration - and so do databases. They allow for more flexibility, openness and bricolage in the scientific handling of data instead of stiff systems and hierarchical order (Gugerli 2009, 13).

⁷This information can only be accessed when registered and logged in.

Figure 10: Excerpt from the relation diagram. Highlighted are the relations for form 35 (Auth, Rösler and Domscheit, RGK).

The user shall have a working space where they can combine three segments (rim, wall, base) of profile drawings and thus can create their own complete profile. Through the segments the catalogue of forms should be accessible. If the user figures that they created an existing, or interesting, or just a very nice profile, they should see the reconstructed exteriors whereby they learn if they created a chimaera or an existing form. With this concept, researchers, students and everyone interested are encouraged to not only observe but to interact with the data in the groupings. Their definition as forms may be presented as unambiguous in inscriptions, but in reality, they are vague. The Archaeological FormSlider will catch up on this subject and help with exploratory play with the data.

2) The 'relation diagram': In the catalogue text, there are descriptive relationships to other types and forms, which refer to other type designations that are considered known. They often occur as short sentences like comments. And they are not as straightforward as one might wish for. They are descriptive and some are more tangible like "cups of Form 22 were being produced and used alongside plates of Form 12" (Ettlinger et al. 1990, 90). Others then again are very vague, for example: "a few recorded instances of this form suggest that it is a hybrid of Forms 12 and 18" (Ettlinger et al. 1990, 80) or "the form evolves gradually into Form 20" (Ettlinger et al. 1990, 82).

Via a network diagram (fig. 10) these relations, abstracted and grouped, could be displayed and lead to the combination and representation of information and images and thus make descriptive information accessible and more visible. This could reopen the data to queries concerning the production, function, find contexts and chronology but also to the vaguer relations of possible hybridity or the like. It is planned to implement these concepts once the data transferral into the iDAI.world systems is completed.

Synthesis

In this paper we have analysed the different type concepts, chrono-types and form, employed in the published catalogues of two thing edition projects, CRFB and *Conspectus*, with the help of the epistemological concepts of inscriptions and trade-offs. Based on these analyses we have introduced a module and

two concepts to enhance the quality and the linking of the catalogues data in the digital environment.

Both catalogues are the outcome of research collaborations on collecting and structuring existing knowledge and standardising terminology by creating what is called *Normdaten*, originally a working tool in libraries. But *Normdaten* as special type of structured data are becoming more relevant in the course of the ongoing digital transformation and linking of research data in general, as they are the nodes in the growing data network. By transferring terminology and information of recognised and frequently referenced catalogues on Roman finds and associated regional finds (CRFB) as well as type designation for plain *terra sigillata* (*Conspectus*) we aimed at providing archaeological *Normdaten* for the growing net of digital archaeological data collections.

Determining the possibilities and limitations of type inscriptions in specific catalogue entries or structures by explicating the trade-off, that is the reduction of certain information in order to be able to amplify standardisation processes or vice versa, has enabled us to develop digital strategies to mitigate these trade-offs. We have introduced a typochronological module conceptualised as a tree model, that allows for a scalable designation and dating of objects and types as it links existing type definitions. Currently the module is limited to the types and their concordances used within the CRFB-context. Nevertheless ca. 3,000 different types are included in the database. The types will cover every Roman finds group, except for coins, which will be referenced from the database afe.dainst.org. Thus, we are able to enhance the type and dating information in the CRFB's data entries.

The *Conspectus*, on the other hand, already has a scalable type concept, that is a grouping of existing types of plain *terra sigillata* on the basis of shape, the possibility of a more precise type identification within the group, plus an independent and simple inscription system. In this sense, the *Conspectus* system is a demo version of the typochronological module. By implementing the *Conspectus* forms into the long-standing large data stock iDAI.objects, the benefits of the type concept's trade-off – amplification of standard denomination and description – as well as its flexibility can be used to link data. In the context of this data collection, the *Conspectus* forms now serve as *Normdaten*, offering nodes within the net of data.

Archaeological type concepts can be used in hierarchical data structures, in this article represented by the tree model, as well as in flat structure hierarchies of data networks. But, while tree models do not need special knowledge because they guide the user, data networks need informed users who are able to navigate through the data and evaluate the knowledge created by linkage. A thesaurus (e.g., thesauri.dainst.org) as well as digital navigation for data access and representation, proposed on the previous pages in mode of a puzzle and a relation diagram, are therefore essential.

Perspectives

Today, digitising publications no longer just means, making PDFs available in open access, but also processing information that has already been published for the web 2.0 LOUD and FAIR. Our aim is no longer to publish discrete collections of material, but the joint processing and networking of connectable data on things, not only relevant for archaeology but also for other disciplines and transdisciplinary research. This also corresponds to the current numerous funding formats of national and international research data infrastructures, such as [Research Data Infrastructure for the Material Remains of Human History](#) (NFDI4Ojects) and [AriadnePlus](#). Dynamic publishing, in turn, allows information about new finds to be published and linked more quickly, but also, for example, to represent different typologies and dating approaches. Based on the insights gained with the transfer and the accompanying transformation of data on paper to bytes and their representation in the digital medium, we have derived concepts for dynamic publication of archaeological research data. In the long-term project [disiecta membra. Stone Architecture and Urbanism in Roman Germany](#) (2023–2046), which is funded by the Academy of Sciences

and Literature Mainz, we are going to create a dynamic and linked digital edition for archaeological (reused) components of Roman stone architecture, its urban contextualisation and its find and collection histories in an interdisciplinary team. We will critically accompany the development and work with the digital edition by analysing its underlying scholarly practices and user data. The digital edition will use the [CIDOC-CRM](#) ontology and the Integrated Authority File ([GND](#)) for its formal structure. Research data and analyses will be published on the research data platforms [iDAI.world](#) and [Propylaeum](#).

Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

Funding

The authors declare that they have received no specific funding for this study

References

- Almgren, Oscar. 1923. Studien über Nordeuropäische Fibelformen der ersten nachchristlichen Jahrhunderte mit Berücksichtigung der provinzialrömischen und südrussischen Formen. 2. Ed. Leipzig: Kabitzsch, 1923.
- Archiv RGK CFZab-4. Akte: Protokolle Arbeitstreffen 1986-1989. Protokoll der Conspectus-Tagung Castelen, 14.–15.11.1987. <https://archives.dainst.org/index.php/de-dai-rgk-a-cfzab>
- Atlante delle forme ceramiche 2. Ceramica fine romana nel bacino mediterraneo. Enciclopedia dell'arte antica classica e orientale. Rom, 1985.
- Auth, Frederic, and Hans-Ulrich Voss. 2021. «Bemerkungen zu „Typologie 2.0 – Datenbanken in der Archäologie: Das Europäische Projekt Artefacts.mom.fr.» *Germania* 98 (2020), 214–222. <https://doi.org/10.11588/ger.2020.85272>
- Benecke, Norbert, and Philipp v. Rummel, Eds. 2021. Das Zentralinstitut für Alte Geschichte und Archäologie (ZIAGA) und das Deutsche Archäologische Institut (DAI): Erinnerungen und Berichte aus der Vor- und Nachwendzeit (1975–2010). Berlin: Deutsches Archäologisches Institut, 2021.
- Bohn, Volker, Ed. 1988. Typologie. Internationale Beiträge zur Poetik 2. Frankfurt: Suhrkamp, 1988.
- Bowker, Geoffrey C. and Susan Leigh Star. 2000. Sorting things out. Classification and its consequences. Cambridge Mass. and London: MIT Press, 2000. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/6352.001.0001>
- CRFB D1: Voss, Hans-Ulrich, Horst Geisler, and Rudolf Laser. Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum. Bonn: R. Habelt, 1994.
- CRFB D2: Laser, Rudolf. Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum. Bonn: R. Habelt, 1995.
- CRFB D3: Voss, Hans-Ulrich, and Michael Erdrich. Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum. Bonn: R. Habelt, 1998.
- CRFB D3 Nachtrag: Hirsch, Klaus, Ralf Lehmphul, and Norbert Kuhlmann. "Römisches" Aus Mecklenburg-Vorpommern. Nachträge Zur Lieferung D 3 Des "Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum". 2006.
- CRFB D4: Teegen, Wolf-Rüdiger, and Michael Erdrich. Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum. Bonn: Habelt, 2002.

- CRFB D5: Erdrich, Michael, Claus von Carnap-Bornheim, Gerhard Stawingo, and Volker Hilberg. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Bonn: R. Habelt, 2004.
- CRFB D6: Becker, Matthias, and Fabian Gall. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Bonn: R. Habelt, 2006.
- CRFB D7: Berke, Stephan., and Daniel Bérenger. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Bonn: Habelt, 2009.
- CRFB D8.1: Dušek, Sigrid., and Matthias Becker. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Wiesbaden: Reichert, 2017.
- CRFB PL1: Nowakowski, Wojciech. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum: Korpus Znalezisk Rzymskich Z Europejskiego Barbaricum*. Instytut Archeologii Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, 2001.
- CRFB PL2: Kaczanowski, Piotr, Jarosław Bodzek, Andrzej Przychodni, and Katarzyna Zuch. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum = Korpus Znalezisk Rzymskich Z Europejskiego Barbaricum*. Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności Uniwersytet Jagielloński Uniwersytet Warszawski, 2017.
- CRFB PL3: Jakubczyk, Ireneusz, Aleksander Bursche, and Magdalena Mączyńska. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum = Korpus Znalezisk Rzymskich Z Europejskiego Barbaricum*. Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności, Uniwersytet Jagielloński, Uniwersytet Warszawski, 2018.
- CRFB PL Supplement 1: Kolendo, Jerzy, Jacek Andrzejowski, Aleksander Bursche, and Wojciech Nowakowski. *Korpus Znalezisk Rzymskich Z Europejskiego Barbaricum: Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Warszawa: Instytut Archeologii Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, 1998.
- CRFB PL Supplement 2: Kolendo, Jerzy, Aleksander Bursche, and Borys Paszkiewicz. *Korpus Znalezisk Rzymskich Z Europejskiego Barbaricum: Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Warszawa: Instytut Archeologii Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, 2001.
- CRFB PL Supplement 3: Ciołek, Renata, Aleksander Bursche, and Roksany Chowaniec. *Korpus Znalezisk Rzymskich Z Europejskiego Barbaricum: Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Warszawa: Instytut Archeologii Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, 2006.
- CRFB PL Supplement 4: Kokowski, Andrzej, Barbara Niezabitowska-Wiśniewska, and Jolanta Bagińska. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum = Korpus Znalezisk Rzymskich Z Europejskiego Barbaricum*. Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności, Uniwersytet Marii Curie-Skłodowskiej w Lublinie, Uniwersytet Jagielloński, Uniwersytet Warszawski, 2021.
- CRFB Litauen: Michelbertas, Mykolas. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Vilnius: Universität Vilnius, Lehrstuhl für Archäologie, 2001.
- CRFB U1: Vaday, Andrea H., and Friderika Horváth. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Budapest: Akaprint, 2005.
- CRFB RO1: Grumeza, Lavinia. *Corpus Der Römischen Funde Im Europäischen Barbaricum*. Cluj-Napoca: Editura Mega, 2019.
- Eco, Umberto. 2009. *Die unendliche Liste*. München: Carl Hanser Verlag, 2009.
- Eggers, Hans Jürgen. 1951. *Der römische Import im freien Germanien*. Hamburg: Hamburgisches Museum für Völkerkunde und Vorgeschichte, 1951.
- Ettlinger, Elisabeth, Bettina Hedinger, Bettina Hoffmann, Philip M. Kenrick, Giuseppe Pucci, Katrin Roth-Rubi, Gerwulf Schneider, Siegmund von Schnurbein, Colin Wells, and Susanne Zabehlicky-Scheffenecker, Eds. 1990. *Conspectus Formarum Terrae Sigillatae Italico Modo Confectae. Materialien Zur Römisch-Germanischen Keramik 10*. Bonn: Habelt, 1990.
- <https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/000255878>.

- Goudineau, Christian. 1968. *Fouilles De L'École Française De Rome à Bolsena (Poggio Moscini) 1962-1967: 4. La Céramique Aretine Lisse*. Paris: De Boccard, 1968.
- Grumeza, Lavinia. 2020. *Corpus of Roman Finds in the European Barbaricum. Romania 1. Ancient Civilizations from Scythia to Siberia* 26, 2 (2020): 332-349, <https://doi.org/10.1163/15700577-12341377>
- Gugerli, David. 2009. *Suchmaschinen: Die Welt als Datenbank*. Frankfurt a.M.: Suhrkamp, 2009.
- Hofmann, Kerstin P. 2014. «Auf der Suche nach der Jastorf-Fibel. Die ältereisenzeitlichen Plattenfibeln Norddeutschlands - eine Leitform?» In *Das Jastorf-Konzept und die vorrömische Eisenzeit im nördlichen Mitteleuropa. Beiträge der Internationalen Tagung zum einhundertjährigen Jubiläum der Veröffentlichung der Ältesten Urnenfriedhöfe bei Uelzen und Lüneburg durch Gustav Schwantes 18.-22.05.2011 in Bad Bevensen. Veröffentlichungen des Archäologischen Museums Hamburg* 105, ed. by J. Brandt, B. Rauchfuß, 129–142. Hamburg: Archäologisches Museum, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.11588/propylaeumdok.00003892>
- Hofmann, Kerstin P. 2018. «Dingidentitäten und Objekttransformationen. Einige Überlegungen zur Edition von archäologischen Funden.» In *Objekt epistemologien. Zum Verhältnis von Dingen und Wissen. Berlin Studies of the Ancient World* 59, ed. by Markus Hilgert, Kerstin P. Hofmann, Henrike Simon, 179–215. Berlin: Edition Topoi, 2018. <https://dx.doi.org/10.17171/3-59>
- Hofmann, Kerstin P., and Stefan Schreiber. 2015. «Raumwissen und Wissensräume. Vielfältige Figurationen eines weiten Forschungsfeldes für die Altertumswissenschaften.» *eTopoi. Journal for Ancient Studies Special Volume* 5, 2015, 9–37. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17169/refubium-23482>
- Hofmann, Kerstin P., Susanne Grunwald, Franziska Lang, Ulrike Peter, Katja Rösler, Louise Rokohl, Stefan Schreiber, Karsten Tolle, and David Wigg-Wolf. 2019. «Ding-Editionen. Vom archäologischen (Be-)Fund übers Corpus ins Netz.» *e-Forschungsberichte des DAI* 2019/2, 1–12. <https://publications.dainst.org/journals/efb/2236/6674>; <https://doi.org/10.34780/s7a5-71 aj>
- Jung, Matthias. 2017. «Wanderungsnarrative in Der Ur- Und Frühgeschichtsforschung.» In *Vom Wandern der Völker: Migrationserzählungen in Den Altertumswissenschaften*, ed. by Wiedemann, Felix., Kerstin P. Hofmann, and Hans-Joachim Gehrke, 161–187. Berlin: Edition Topoi, 2017. DOI 10.17171/3-41
- Kunow, Jürgen. 1998. «Die Hauptserie Der Augenfibeln: Gruppe III, Fig: 45–54.» In *100 Jahre Fibelformen Nach Oscar Almgren: Internationale Arbeitstagung 25.–28.05.1997, Kleinmachnow, Land Brandenburg*, ed. by Michaela Aufleger, 93–118. Wünsdorf: Brandenburgisches Landesmuseum für Ur- u. Frühgeschichte, 1998.
- Latour, Bruno. 2002. *Die Hoffnung der Pandora*. Frankfurt: Suhrkamp, 2002.
- Müller-Wille, Staffan, and Isabelle Charmantier. 2012. «Lists as Research Technologies.» *Isis* 103, 2012, 743–752. <https://doi.org/10.1086/669048>
- Müller-Wille, Staffan. 2017. «Names and Numbers: "Data" in Classical Natural History, 1758–1859.» *Osiris* 32, 2017, 109–128. <https://doi.org/10.1086/693560>
- Oxford Latin Dictionary. 1968. Souter, Alexander, and Peter G. W. Glare (Ed.). *Oxford Latin Dictionary*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1968.
- Rösler, Katja. 2019. *Typus, Kultur und Taxonomie. Metaphern in der Fachsprache der Prähistorischen Archäologie am Beispiel der Schriften Jens Lünings*. Freiburger Archäologische Studien 10. Rahden/Westfalen: Verlag Marie Leidorf, 2019.

- Rösler, Katja, Kerstin P. Hofmann and David Wigg-Wolf. 2022. Archäologie und Digitalität: Vernetzte Daten und Welten / Archaeology and Digitality: networked data and worlds. in: Bánffy, Eszter, Kerstin P. Hofmann and Alexander Gramsch (Ed.). Europa Archaeologica. Die RGK und ihre Forschungen / The RGK and its research activities. Frankfurt a. M., 2022, 200-215. [Link](#)).
- Rossi, Paolo. 2000. Logic and the Art of Memory. The Quest for a Universal Language. London: The Athlone Press, 2000.
- Schreiber, Stefan. 2018. Wandernde Dinge als Assemblagen. Neo-Materialistische Perspektiven zum ‚Römischen Import‘ im ‚Mitteldeutschen Barbaricum‘. Berlin: Edition Topoi, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.17171/3-52>
- Tempelmann-Maczyńska, Magdalena. 1985. Die Perlen der römischen Kaiserzeit und der frühen Phase der Völkerwanderungszeit im mitteleuropäischen Barbaricum. Mainz am Rhein: Verlag Philipp von Zabern, 1985.
- Thiery, Florian. 2019. Sphere 7 Data. LOUD and FAIR Data for the Research Community. Zenodo 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2643470>
- Voss, Hans-Ulrich, and Claus-Michael Hüssen. 2017. «Corpus der Römischen Funde im europäischen Barbaricum – Rückblick und Ausblick.» In Roman Frontier Studies 2009: Proceedings of the XXI International Congress of Roman Frontier Studies (Limes Congress) Held at Newcastle-upon-Tyne in August 2009, ed. by N. Hodgson, Paul T. Bidwell, and Judith Schachtmann, 318–326. Oxford: Archaeopress Publishing Ltd., 2017. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv177tk1m.52>
- Wielowiejski, Jerzy. 1970. Kontakty Noricum I Pannonii Z Ludami Północnymi. Wrocław/ Warszawa/ Kraków: Polskiej Akademii Nauk, 1970.

Authors

Frederic Auth (RGK / Goethe University Frankfurt) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1948-9876>

Katja Rösler (RGK) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7520-7079>

Wenke Domscheit (RGK) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4765-0591>

Kerstin P. Hofmann (RGK) <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4405-5751>